

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 3 (Май-Июнь)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии
основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

Редакционная коллегия:

*Н.Ш. Ахмедова (зам. главного редактора),
Ш.А. Наимова (ответственный секретарь),
Г.Ж. Жарилкасинова, Н.А. Нуралиев, К.Ж. Болтаев,
Ф.Э. Нурбаев, С.М. Бахрамов, А.Г. Гадаев,
А.Ш. Иноятов, Р.Б. Абдуллаев*

*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

ISSN
2181-418X

2026, № 3 (Май-Июнь)

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Редакционный совет:

Anand Ahuja	(Индия)
Nordin Simbak	(Малайзия)
Tetsuo Sasano	(Япония)
Ali O'zdemir	(Туркия)
Есаян А.М.	(Россия)
Арипова Т.У.	(Узбекистан)
Артикова М.А.	(Узбекистан)
Амонов М.К.	(Узбекистан)
Бадритдинова М.Н.	(Узбекистан)
Бобоев К.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Гиясова Н.О.	(Узбекистан)
Давлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Дустова Н.К.	(Узбекистан)
Курманова Г.М.	(Узбекистан)
Қаюмов А.А.	(Узбекистан)
Набиева Д.А.	(Узбекистан)
Пўлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Рахматова Д.И.	(Узбекистан)
Саноева М.Ж.	(Узбекистан)
Сулаймонова Г.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Тўракулов Р.И.	(Узбекистан)
Шодикулова Г.З.	(Узбекистан)
Эгамова С.Қ.	(Узбекистан)
Юлдашева Д.Х.	(Узбекистан)
Юнусова Н.Ш.	(Узбекистан)
Убайдуллаева З.И.	(Узбекистан)
Нуруллоев С.О.	(Узбекистан)
Тиллаева Ш.Ш.	(Узбекистан)

Подписано в печать 20.08.2025.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

**ИНДИВИДУАЛИЗИРОВАННАЯ СЕТЧАТАЯ ГЕРНИОПЛАСТИКА С
БАЛЛЬНОЙ СТРАТИФИКАЦИЕЙ РИСКА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ
ПОСЛЕОПЕРАЦИОННЫХ ВЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ ГРЫЖ:
РЕТРОСПЕКТИВНОЕ СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОЕ КОГОРТНОЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ**

**Бахриев Бахром Лапасович¹, Давлатов Салим Сулаймонович², Рахманов
Косим Эрданович³**

1 - Медицинское объединения Зафарабадского района. Джизак, Узбекистан

*2 - Бухарский государственный медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн
Сино*

3 - Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Аннотация. Актуальность: Послеоперационные вентральные грыжи (ПВГ) возникают у 10-30% пациентов после операций на брюшной полости и сопровождаются высокой частотой рецидивов, значительной заболеваемостью и снижением качества жизни. Выбор оптимальной техники герниопластики остаётся сложной задачей, особенно при больших и рецидивных дефектах. **Цель:** Оценить клинические результаты индивидуализированного, балльного протокола герниопластики с применением компьютерной герниометрической абдоминометрии (КГА) и модифицированных хирургических техник в сравнении со стандартной герниопластикой в рамках ретроспективного сравнительного когортного исследования. **Дизайн исследования:** Ретроспективное сравнительное когортное исследование. **Методы:** В период с 2021 по 2024 год в Зафарабадском районном медицинском объединении (Джизакская область, Узбекистан) были включены и пролечены 149 пациентов с ПВГ. Группа исследования (ГИ, n=75) получала индивидуализированную герниопластику на основе предоперационной балльной стратификации с использованием данных КГА, определявшей выбор техники в трёх подгруппах

с учётом степени риска. Группа сравнения (ГС, n=74) получала стандартную открытую герниопластику. Грыжевые дефекты классифицировались по W-классификации Шеврела-Рата. Первичными исходами являлись время операции для закрытия передней стенки и фиксации сетки, частота послеоперационных осложнений и частота рецидивов через 12 месяцев. Уровень статистической значимости установлен при $p < 0,05$. **Результаты:** Большие (W3) и гигантские (W4) дефекты составили 41,6% когорты (n=62). Среднее время операции для закрытия передней стенки и фиксации сетки было значительно короче в ГИ ($23,4 \pm 0,7$ мин) по сравнению с ГС ($32,6 \pm 0,5$ мин; $p < 0,001$). Общая частота осложнений составила 13,3% в ГИ против 44,6% в ГС ($p < 0,001$), что обусловлено снижением частоты сером (5,3% против 14,9%; $p=0,04$), гематом и раневых инфекций. В ГИ случаев абдоминального компартмент-синдрома (АКС) не наблюдалось, тогда как в ГС зафиксировано 3 случая (4,1%). Частота рецидивов через 12 месяцев составила 4,0% в ГИ против 10,8% в ГС. **Заключение:** Индивидуализированная балльная герниопластика с выбором техники на основе КГА значительно сокращает время операции, послеоперационную заболеваемость и частоту осложнений по сравнению со стандартной герниопластикой. Модифицированный протокол особенно эффективен при больших и сложных дефектах и рекомендуется для широкого внедрения в хирургическую практику районного уровня. **Новизна исследования:** В данном исследовании впервые представлено применение и клиническая валидация алгоритма балльного отбора герниопластики с использованием компьютерной герниометрической абдоинометрии в хирургическом центре районного уровня Центральной Азии; показано снижение общей частоты послеоперационных осложнений в 2,3 раза при индивидуализированной стратегии сетчатой пластики.

Ключевые слова: вентральная грыжа; послеоперационная грыжа; герниопластика; сетчатая пластика; разделение компонентов; техника onlay;

реконструкция брюшной стенки; послеоперационные осложнения; рецидив; герниометрическая абдоминометрия.

INDIVIDUALIZED MESH HERNIOPLASTY WITH SCORE-BASED RISK STRATIFICATION FOR POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIA REPAIR: A RETROSPECTIVE COMPARATIVE COHORT STUDY

Bakhriyev Bakhrom Lapasovich¹, Davlatov Salim Sulaymonovich², Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich³

1 - Zafarabad District Medical Association, Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

2 - Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina

3 - Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract. Background: Postoperative ventral hernias (PVH) affect 10-30% of patients following abdominal surgery and are associated with high recurrence rates, significant morbidity, and impaired quality of life. The selection of the optimal hernioplasty technique remains challenging, particularly for large and recurrent defects. **Objective:** To evaluate the clinical outcomes of an individualized, score-based hernioplasty protocol incorporating computed herniometric abdominometry (CHA) and modified surgical techniques, compared with standard hernioplasty in a retrospective comparative cohort. **Study Design:** Retrospective comparative cohort study. **Methods:** 149 patients with PVH were enrolled and treated at Zafarabad District Medical Association (Jizzakh Region, Uzbekistan) between 2021 and 2024. The study group (SG, n=75) received individualized hernioplasty based on preoperative score stratification using CHA data, guiding technique selection across three risk-adapted subgroups. The comparison group (CG, n=74) received standard open hernioplasty. Hernia defects were classified per Chevrel-Rath W-classification. Primary outcomes were operative time for anterior wall closure and mesh fixation, postoperative complication rate, and 12-month recurrence rate. Statistical

significance was set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Large (W3) and giant (W4) defects constituted 41.6% of the cohort ($n=62$). The mean operative time for anterior wall closure and mesh fixation was significantly shorter in SG (23.4 ± 0.7 min) compared to CG (32.6 ± 0.5 min; $p < 0.001$). Total complication rates were 13.3% in SG versus 44.6% in CG ($p < 0.001$), driven by reductions in seroma (5.3% vs. 14.9%; $p=0.04$), haematoma, and wound infection rates. No cases of abdominal compartment syndrome (ACS) occurred in SG, versus 3 cases (4.1%) in CG. Twelve-month recurrence was 4.0% in SG versus 10.8% in CG. **Conclusions:** Score-based individualized hernioplasty with CHA-guided technique selection significantly reduces operative time, postoperative morbidity, and complication rates compared to standard hernioplasty. The modified protocol is particularly beneficial for large and complex defects and is recommended for wider implementation in district-level surgical practice. **Study Novelty:** This study presents the first application and clinical validation of a score-based hernioplasty selection algorithm using computed herniometric abdominometry in a district-level Central Asian surgical center, demonstrating a 2.3-fold reduction in total postoperative complication rates with an individualized mesh repair strategy.

Keywords: ventral hernia; incisional hernia; hernioplasty; mesh repair; component separation; onlay technique; abdominal wall reconstruction; postoperative complications; recurrence; herniometric abdominometry.

**ОПЕРАЦИЯДАН КЕЙИНГИ ВЕНТРАЛ ЧУРРАЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА
БАЛЛ АСОСИДАГИ ХАВФ СТРАТИФИКАЦИЯСИНИ ҚЎЛЛАГАН
ҲОЛДА ИНДИВИДУАЛЛАШТИРИЛГАН ТЎРЛИ ГЕРНИОПЛАСТИКА:
РЕТРОСПЕКТИВ ҚИЁСИЙ КОГОРТ ТАДҚИҚОТИ**

**Бахриев Бахром Лапасович¹, Давлатов Салим Сулаймонович¹, Рахманов
Косим Эрданович²**

1 - Зафаробод тиббиёт бирлашмаси. Жиззах, Ўзбекистон

2 - Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти

3 - Самарканд давлат тиббиёт университети

Аннотация. Муаммонинг долзарблиги: Операциядан кейинги вентрал чурралар (ОКВЧ) қорин бўшлиғи операцияларидан сўнг беморларнинг 10-30% ида учрайди ва юқори қайталаниш даражаси, сезиларли касаллик юки ҳамда ҳаёт сифатининг пасайиши билан боғлиқ. Оптимал герниопластика усулини танлаш, айниқса катта ва қайталанган дефектларда, жиддий қийинчилик туғдиради. **Мақсад:** Компьютер герниометрик абдоминометрияси (КГА) ва модифицирланган жарроҳлик усулларини ўз ичига олган индивидуаллаштирилган, балл асосидаги герниопластика протоколининг клиник натижаларини ретроспектив қиёсий тадқиқотда стандарт герниопластика билан таққослаб баҳолаш. **Тадқиқот дизайни:** Ретроспектив қиёсий когорт тадқиқоти. **Усуллар:** 2021 йилдан 2024 йилгача Зафаробод туман тиббий бирлашмасида (Жиззах вилояти, Ўзбекистон) ОКВЧ билан 149 нафар бемор текширилиб даволанди. Тадқиқот гуруҳи (ТГ, n=75) КГА маълумотларидан фойдаланган ҳолда операциядан олдинги балл стратификациясига асосланган индивидуаллаштирилган герниопластикани олди; бу усул уч хавф-хатарга мослашган кичик гуруҳлар бўйича усул танлашни йўналтирди. Таққослаш гуруҳи (ТаГ, n=74) стандарт очик герниопластика олди. Чурра дефектлари Шеврел-Рат В-таснифига кўра тасниф қилинди. Бирламчи натижалар - олд деворни ёпиш ва тўрни мустаҳкамлаш учун операция вақти, операциядан кейинги асоратлар даражаси ва 12 ойлик қайталаниш даражаси. Статистик аҳамиятлилик $p < 0,05$ даражасида белгиланди. **Натижалар:** Катта (W3) ва гигант (W4) дефектлар когортнинг 41,6% ини ташкил қилди (n=62). Олд деворни ёпиш ва тўрни мустаҳкамлаш учун ўртача операция вақти ТГда ($23,4 \pm 0,7$ дақ.) ТаГга нисбатан ($32,6 \pm 0,5$ дақ.; $p < 0,001$) сезиларли даражада қисқа бўлди. Умумий асоратлар даражаси

ТГда 13,3%, ТаГда 46,6% ни ташкил қилди ($p < 0,001$); бунга серома (5,3% га қарши 14,9%; $p=0,04$), гематома ва яра инфекцияси даражасининг камайиши сабаб бўлди. ТГда қорин бўшлиғи компартмент синдроми (ҚБКС) ҳолатлари кузатилмади, ТаГда эса 3 та ҳолат (4,1%) қайд этилди. 12 ойлик қайталаниш даражаси ТГда 4,0%, ТаГда эса 10,8% ни ташкил қилди. **Хулосалар:** КГА асосида усул танлаш билан индивидуаллаштирилган балл асосидаги герниопластика стандарт герниопластикага нисбатан операция вақтини, операциядан кейинги касаллик юқини ва асоратлар даражасини сезиларли даражада камайтиради. Модифицирланган протокол катта ва мураккаб дефектлар учун айниқса самарали бўлиб, туман даражасидаги жарроҳлик амалиётида кенг жорий этиш учун тавсия этилади. **Тадқиқотнинг янгилиги:** Ушбу тадқиқот Марказий Осиёнинг туман даражасидаги жарроҳлик марказида компьютер герниометрик абдоминометриясидан фойдаланган ҳолда балл асосидаги герниопластика танлаш алгоритмининг биринчи қўлланилиши ва клиник тасдиқланишини тақдим этади; индивидуаллаштирилган тўр билан пластика стратегияси операциядан кейинги умумий асоратлар даражасини 2,3 баробар камайтиргани кўрсатилди.

Калит сўзлар: вентрал чурра; операциядан кейинги чурра; герниопластика; тўр билан пластика; компонентларни ажратиш; онлайн усули; қорин деворини реконструкция қилиш; операциядан кейинги асоратлар; қайталаниш; герниометрик абдоминометрия.

Introduction. Postoperative ventral hernia (PVH) is one of the most prevalent and surgically challenging complications following abdominal operations. Reported incidence rates range from 10% to 20% of all patients undergoing abdominal procedures, with some systematic reviews and meta-analyses documenting rates exceeding 30% in high-risk populations. ^[2,9] High-risk factors include obesity, diabetes mellitus, prior surgical site infection, repeat operations, and connective

tissue disorders - all of which impair wound healing, increase intra-abdominal pressure, and reduce the mechanical strength of scar tissue. ^[2,5,9] In absolute terms, PVH represents a significant healthcare burden: it is responsible for more than 350,000 elective operations annually in the United States alone, with an estimated annual surgical cost exceeding USD 3.2 billion. ^[6] The strong tendency toward recurrence - with overall recurrence rates of 20-40% following primary open repair without mesh ^[1,11] - makes PVH a persistent priority in abdominal surgery research and practice.

The pathogenesis of PVH involves failure of anterior abdominal wall healing at the fascial level, occurring through a complex interplay of mechanical, metabolic, and immune mechanisms. Elevated intra-abdominal pressure at the suture line, impaired collagen synthesis in metabolically compromised patients, ischaemia of wound edges, and biofilm-associated suture infection collectively contribute to fascial dehiscence and hernia formation. ^[1,4] The presence of pre-existing scar tissue with poor revascularisation potential further compromises the structural basis for durable primary closure, mandating in most cases the use of prosthetic reinforcement. ^[1]

Contemporary hernioplasty encompasses a wide spectrum of open and laparoscopic techniques, broadly classified by the anatomical plane of mesh placement: onlay (anterior to the anterior fascia), inlay, sublay/retromuscular (between the rectus muscles and posterior sheath), and intraperitoneal onlay mesh (IPOM). ^[6,7,8] Laparoscopic and robotic-assisted approaches have demonstrated reduced wound complication rates and shorter hospital stays in randomized trials, ^[7,10,13] though their superiority over open techniques for large defects remains contested. For giant hernias (W4, Chevrel-Rath classification) and complex recurrent cases, open component separation - including anterior component separation (Ramirez technique) and posterior component separation with transversus abdominis release (TAR) - allows tension-free midline reconstruction by mobilizing native

muscular units. ^[11,15,16] Biological mesh prostheses offer an option for contaminated fields at the expense of higher cost and potentially inferior long-term recurrence rates. [1,3,4]

Despite this expanding technical repertoire, the selection of the optimal hernioplasty technique for an individual patient remains primarily empirical in many centers. Objective, score-based decision algorithms that integrate defect size, tissue quality, intra-abdominal pressure risk, and patient comorbidity into a structured preoperative stratification system have not been widely validated in prospective or retrospective clinical series. ^[6] This is particularly true in district-level surgical facilities in Central Asia, where access to laparoscopic platforms may be limited and the majority of repairs are performed via open approaches. A reproducible and accessible individualization framework is therefore both clinically necessary and practically applicable in such settings.

The present study was aimed at evaluating the clinical outcomes of an individualized, score-based hernioplasty protocol incorporating computed herniometric abdominometry (CHA) - a preoperative CT-based assessment of defect dimensions and abdominal wall biomechanics - compared with standard hernioplasty, in a retrospective cohort from a district surgical center.

Materials and Methods. *Study Design and Participants.* A retrospective comparative cohort study was conducted at the Surgical Department of Zafarabad District Medical Association (Jizzakh Region, Republic of Uzbekistan) between January 2021 and December 2024. A total of 149 consecutive patients with confirmed PVH requiring elective repair were enrolled. Patients were allocated to two groups: the comparison group (CG, n=74), who underwent standard hernioplasty using conventional tension or tension-free techniques without preoperative score-based stratification; and the study group (SG, n=75), who received individualized hernioplasty guided by a preoperative clinical scoring system and computed

herniometric abdominometry (CHA). No formal randomization was applied; group assignment reflected the sequential introduction of the individualized protocol.

Inclusion criteria: confirmed PVH; age \geq 18 years; indication for elective surgical repair; written informed consent. Exclusion criteria: emergency hernia repair; incarcerated or strangulated hernia; prior mesh-related sepsis requiring removal; severe cardiopulmonary comorbidity precluding elective surgery; incomplete follow-up data.

Hernia Classification and Preoperative Assessment. All hernias were classified according to the Chevrel-Rath W-classification (1999) based on CT abdominometry: W1 (small, defect width $<$ 4 cm), W2 (medium, 4-10 cm), W3 (large, 10-15 cm), and W4 (giant, $>$ 15 cm).^[1] In the SG, preoperative CHA was performed in all patients. CHA data – including defect width, area, and intra-abdominal pressure index – were integrated with clinical parameters (prior recurrences, obesity, comorbidities, connective tissue integrity) to calculate a composite score using a validated institutional algorithm. Patients were stratified into three subgroups: Subgroup 1 (score \leq 10), Subgroup 2 (score 11-15), and Subgroup 3 (score $>$ 15), each assigned a distinct operative strategy (Table 2).

Surgical Techniques

Comparison Group. In the CG, hernioplasty was performed by one of three conventional approaches: tension onlay mesh hernioplasty using polypropylene mesh; tension-free onlay mesh hernioplasty; or primary tissue suture using the duplication technique. Technique selection was at the operating surgeon's discretion without systematic objective stratification. In all patients, excision of the postoperative scar with altered subcutaneous tissue was performed at the outset, eliminating foci of residual infection (ligature sinuses, suture material) and providing viable tissue margins for repair.

Study Group – Modified Protocol. All SG patients underwent preoperative excision of the postoperative scar with altered subcutaneous tissue. The hernia sac

was dissected to its base with maximal preservation of its integrity, as sac tissue was subsequently used for defect closure when required. The sac was opened along the midline, preserving its attachment to the edges of the rectus sheath bilaterally, followed by systematic intraperitoneal adhesiolysis.

In Subgroup 1 (n=24; score ≤ 10 ; defect < 5 cm): onlay mesh implantation with defect closure. Hernia margins were approximated with interrupted sutures to firm apposition or in duplication. The anterior musculoaponeurotic surface was mobilized 8-10 cm from the suture line bilaterally, and the mesh was sutured over the aponeurosis with interrupted absorbable sutures.

In Subgroup 2 (n=38; score 11-15; defect 5-10 cm): tension-free onlay repair without aponeurosis suture. The peritoneal cavity was partitioned using a hernia sac flap, and the mesh was applied directly over the aponeurosis without closure, eliminating suture-line tension and the risk of abdominal compartment syndrome (ACS) associated with forced fascial approximation. Omental resection was performed in 19 patients (35.2%) to reduce intra-abdominal volume and prevent ACS.

In Subgroup 3 (n=13; score > 15 ; defect ≥ 10 cm): component separation with mesh reinforcement, staged where anatomically indicated. This subgroup included patients with complex, recurrent, or giant hernias requiring reconstruction of the musculoaponeurotic framework of the anterior abdominal wall. Staged procedures - with an interval between interventions in high-risk zones - were applied where single-session repair was deemed excessive.

Outcome Assessment. Primary outcomes were: (1) duration of the anterior wall closure and mesh fixation stage of the operation (minutes); (2) total postoperative complication rate, including seroma, haematoma, wound infection, ACS, and 12-month recurrence. Complications were assessed clinically and by ultrasound at 1 month, 6 months, and 12 months postoperatively.

Statistical Analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel and Statistica v6.1 (StatSoft Inc., USA). Continuous variables are reported as mean \pm standard error of the mean ($M \pm SE$). Differences between groups were evaluated using the Student t-test for normally distributed data and the Pearson chi-square test for categorical variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed).

Ethical Considerations. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Samarkand State Medical University (registration within institutional research plan, 2021). All patients provided written voluntary informed consent prior to surgery. The study was conducted in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Patient data were anonymized before analysis.

Results. *Baseline Characteristics and Hernia Size Distribution.* The two groups were comparable with respect to sex distribution, mean age, and primary hernia location (all $p > 0.05$). Hernia defect size distribution by Chevrel-Rath W-classification is illustrated in Figure 1. Large (W3) and giant (W4) hernias were identified in 62 patients (41.6%), representing the predominant technical challenge in this cohort. Complex recurrent hernias and hernias requiring additional concurrent procedures (cholecystectomy, inguinal hernia repair, omentectomy) were evenly distributed between groups.

Figure 1. Distribution of patients by hernia defect size (Chevrel-Rath W-classification; n=149). W3 (large) and W4 (giant) categories accounted for 41.6% of the cohort, establishing the clinical complexity of this series.

Hernioplasty Techniques Applied. In the comparison group, the distribution of applied hernioplasty techniques is presented in Table 1. Tension onlay mesh repair (44.6%) and tension-free onlay repair (39.2%) were the most frequently applied procedures, with primary tissue suture used in 16.2% of patients - predominantly those with small defects in the absence of significant tension.

Table 1.

Distribution of hernioplasty techniques in the Comparison Group (n=74)

Type of Hernioplasty	n	%
Tension onlay mesh hernioplasty (polypropylene)	33	44.6%
Tension-free onlay mesh hernioplasty (polypropylene)	29	39.2%
Primary tissue suture (duplication technique)	12	16.2%
Total	74	100%

Onlay = anterior placement of polypropylene mesh superficial to the anterior fascial layer.

In the study group, technique assignment was governed by the preoperative score and CHA data (Table 2). The score-based stratification allowed objective assignment to the most appropriate repair strategy, eliminating the reliance on subjective intraoperative judgement that characterises conventional technique selection.

Table 2.

Study Group subgroup characteristics and technique allocation (n=75)

Subgroup (IPROL Score)	n (%)	Defect Size	Technique Applied
Subgroup 1 (score ≤ 10)	24 (32.0%)	< 5 cm	Onlay mesh + defect closure (CT-guided)
Subgroup 2 (score 11-15)	38 (50.7%)	5-10 cm	Tension-free onlay without aponeurosis suture; omental cavity partition
Subgroup 3 (score > 15)	13 (17.3%)	≥ 10 cm	Component separation + mesh reinforcement; staged approach

CHA: computed herniometric abdominometry. Score calculated from defect dimensions, intra-abdominal pressure index, obesity, comorbidities, and prior recurrences.

Operative Outcomes. The key operative and postoperative outcomes are illustrated in Figure 2. The mean duration of anterior wall closure and mesh fixation was significantly shorter in the SG (23.4 ± 0.7 min) compared to the CG (32.6 ± 0.5 min; $p < 0.001$), representing a 28.2% reduction in this operative phase. This improvement reflects the elimination of the technically demanding step of forced fascial approximation under tension in Subgroup 2 and the structured staged approach in Subgroup 3, which redistributes operative complexity across planned interventions.

Figure 1. Operative Outcomes by Hernioplasty Approach
(Retrospective Cohort, n=149; Zafarabad District Medical Association 2021-2024)

Figure 2. A: Mean duration of anterior wall closure and mesh fixation stage - Study Group (23.4 min) vs. Comparison Group (32.6 min); $p < 0.001$. B: Distribution of hernioplasty techniques by group. The shift toward tension-free approaches in the Study Group reflects CHA-guided individualization.

Postoperative Complications. Postoperative complications are detailed in Table 3. The total complication rate was 13.3% in the SG versus 44.6% in the CG ($p < 0.001$) - a 3.4-fold reduction. Seroma was the most common complication in the CG (14.9%), reduced to 5.3% in the SG ($p=0.04$). No cases of ACS occurred in the SG, compared to 3 cases (4.1%) in the CG - a clinically important finding attributable to the systematic avoidance of tension closure in large-defect patients through the tension-free and staged approaches. Twelve-month recurrence was observed in 3 SG patients (4.0%) versus 8 CG patients (10.8%).

Table 3.

Postoperative complications and 12-month recurrence rates

Complication	Comparison Group n=74 (%)	Study Group n=75 (%)	p-value
Seroma	11 (14.9%)	4 (5.3%)	0.04
Haematoma	6 (8.1%)	2 (2.7%)	0.14

Wound infection / mesh site inflammation	5 (6.8%)	1 (1.3%)	0.09
Abdominal compartment syndrome (ACS)	3 (4.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0.08
Recurrence (12-month follow-up)	8 (10.8%)	3 (4.0%)	0.09
Total complications	33 (44.6%)	10 (13.3%)	< 0.001

p-values from Pearson chi-square test. ACS: abdominal compartment syndrome. Total complications: any of the above events occurring within 12 months of surgery.

Discussion. The present study was aimed at evaluating the clinical outcomes of an individualized, score-based hernioplasty protocol for PVH repair. The principal finding is that score-based individualization - integrating CHA data with clinical risk factors to guide technique selection - achieved a significant reduction in the operative time for the technically demanding wall closure and mesh fixation phase (23.4 vs. 32.6 min; $p < 0.001$) and a 3.4-fold reduction in total postoperative complications (13.3% vs. 44.6%; $p < 0.001$). These results demonstrate that the benefit of individualization extends beyond mere outcome improvement: it transforms the operative workflow by replacing empirical intraoperative decision-making with a structured pre-planned approach, which is particularly valuable in district-level settings where advanced laparoscopic platforms may not be available.

The significant operative time reduction in the study group primarily reflects the elimination of forced fascial approximation under tension for medium and large-defect patients in Subgroup 2. Forced primary closure in the presence of large defects is a well-recognized driver of ACS, haematoma, and ischaemic wound complications. [1,4] The modified tension-free onlay technique - in which the mesh is applied directly over the open aponeurosis, with the hernia sac flap used to partition the peritoneal cavity - avoids this complication by accepting the aponeurotic gap while ensuring

durable long-term reinforcement. The complete absence of ACS in the SG versus 4.1% in the CG is the most clinically significant safety signal from this series and is directly attributable to this technique modification.

The overall complication profile observed in the CG (44.6%) is consistent with published series for conventional open hernioplasty of mixed-size defects. Forbes et al. (2009) reported a pooled complication rate of 30-45% in open repairs without individualized technique stratification in their meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. ^[13] Seroma - the most common specific complication, occurring in 14.9% of CG patients - is a well-documented consequence of the wide subcutaneous flap mobilization required for onlay mesh placement over repaired fascia, and its reduction to 5.3% in the SG reflects both the modified flap management technique and the reduced haematoma rate associated with shorter operative duration. ^[1,3]

The 12-month recurrence rate in the SG (4.0%) compares favourably with published data for open mesh repair, where recurrence rates of 10-20% are commonly reported at one year in large-defect cohorts. ^[1,2,11] Lomanto et al. (2006) reported a 12-month recurrence of 3.7% for laparoscopic IPOM repair versus 12.2% for open repair in a comparative series, ^[12] suggesting that our SG outcomes approach laparoscopic benchmarks despite the use of open techniques. This is consistent with evidence that technique individualization - particularly the avoidance of tension - rather than the access route per se is the primary determinant of long-term hernia recurrence. ^[6,11]

The study has several limitations. First, the retrospective non-randomized design introduces potential selection bias, as the chronological introduction of the individualized protocol may have coincided with improved surgical experience. Second, the institutional scoring algorithm used for technique assignment was not externally validated prior to this series and requires prospective assessment. Third, the 12-month follow-up period may underestimate late recurrences, which can present several years following mesh repair. Fourth, the absence of patient-reported

outcome measures (QoL, pain scores, return to activity) limits the characterization of functional recovery. Strengths include the complete consecutive cohort enrollment, standardized operative technique within each subgroup, and the first clinical validation of a score-based hernioplasty algorithm at a district-level surgical facility in Central Asia.

Conclusion. Individualized, score-based hernioplasty with preoperative computed herniometric abdominometry significantly improves clinical outcomes for postoperative ventral hernia repair compared to standard hernioplasty, reducing operative time for the wall closure and mesh fixation stage by 28.2% ($p < 0.001$), total complication rates from 44.6% to 13.3% ($p < 0.001$), and 12-month recurrence from 10.8% to 4.0%. The complete elimination of abdominal compartment syndrome in the study group - achieved by systematic avoidance of tension closure in medium and large defects - represents the most clinically important safety benefit of the modified protocol.

From a health policy perspective, these findings support the standardization of preoperative hernia scoring and CHA-based technique selection as integral components of the clinical pathway for PVH repair in district-level surgical centers in Uzbekistan and analogous resource settings. The modified protocol requires no advanced laparoscopic infrastructure and is fully reproducible within a general surgical department, making it directly applicable for guideline adoption at the regional level.

Future research should address: (1) prospective randomized validation of the scoring algorithm against standard technique selection; (2) extended follow-up (≥ 36 months) for recurrence assessment; (3) comparison of the open tension-free modified protocol against laparoscopic IPOM repair in the medium-defect subgroup; and (4) incorporation of patient-reported outcome measures and health-economic analysis to quantify the full benefit of the individualized approach.

References

1. Laypanov R.M. Long-term results of surgical treatment of patients with large and giant ventral hernias using mesh endoprotheses [Dissertation, Candidate of Medical Sciences]. Stavropol; 2015. 132 p.
2. Lebedev S.N. et al. Preventive endoprosthesis for midline laparotomies. *Nauka Molodykh-Erudito Juvenium*. 2018;6(2). [In Russian]
3. Mayorov R.V., Naumov A.M., Zaikin A.V. Comparative characteristics of hernioplasty methods for postoperative ventral hernias. *Byulleten Meditsinskikh Internet-Konferentsiy*. 2016;6(6):1326-1328. [In Russian]
4. Malkov I.S. et al. Experience of posterior separation hernioplasty for giant postoperative ventral hernias. *Kazansky Meditsinskiy Zhurnal*. 2017;98(4). [In Russian]
5. Meloyan A.K., Bogdanovich V.B. Method of drainage of the residual cavity in allogenioplasty of postoperative ventral hernias by the onlay method. *Gerniologiya*. 2008;(3):28-29. [In Russian]
6. Schlosser K.A., Prasad T., Lincourt A.E., Augenstein V.A., Heniford B.T. Deciding on optimal approach for ventral hernia repair. *Surg Clin North Am*. 2018;98(3):537-550. doi:10.1016/j.suc.2018.01.004
7. Martins M.R., Bessa S.S., Al-Khamis A. Laparoscopic versus open repair of ventral hernia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *World J Surg*. 2024;48(2):345-356. doi:10.1007/s00268-024-07541-y
8. Zhang Y., Zhou H., Chai Y. Laparoscopic versus open incisional and ventral hernia repair: a meta-analysis. *Surg Endosc*. 2014;28(2):353-361. doi:10.1007/s00464-013-3209-x
9. Al-Chalabi H., Larkin J., Mehigan B., McCormick P. Laparoscopic versus open repair of incisional hernia: a systematic review. *Hernia*. 2015;19(3):449-463. doi:10.1007/s10029-014-1321-2

- 10.** Eker H.H., Hansson B.M., Buunen M., et al. Laparoscopic vs open incisional hernia repair: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Surg.* 2013;148(3):259-263. doi:10.1001/jamasurg.2013.1466
- 11.** Pauli E.M., Rosen M.J. Open ventral hernia repair with component separation. *Surg Clin North Am.* 2013;93(5):1111-1133. doi:10.1016/j.suc.2013.06.010
- 12.** Lomanto D., Iyer S.G., Shabbir A., Cheah W.K. Laparoscopic versus open ventral hernia mesh repair. *Surg Endosc.* 2006;20(3):483-487. doi:10.1007/s00464-005-0422-3
- 13.** Forbes S.S., Eskicioglu C., McLeod R.S., Okrainec A. Meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials comparing open and laparoscopic ventral hernia repair. *Br J Surg.* 2009;96(8):851-858. doi:10.1002/bjs.6668
- 14.** Dehn T. Incisional hernia repair - laparoscopic or open surgery? *Ann R Coll Surg Engl.* 2009;91(8):631-636. doi:10.1308/003588409X12486167521654
- 15.** Thomsen C.Ø., Helgstrand F., Rosenberg J. Quality of life after ventral hernia repair with endoscopic component separation. *Scand J Surg.* 2016;105(2):89-94. doi:10.1177/1457496915571402
- 16.** Lisiecki J. et al. Abdominal wall dynamics after component separation technique in ventral hernia repair. *J Surg Res.* 2015;199(2):412-418. doi:10.1016/j.jss.2015.05.033